

MASNAVI GENRE IN UZBEK CLASSICAL POETRY

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The continuity and development of the traditions of previous literature in the new historical conditions is the most important regularity that determines the progressive nature of the literary process. The problem of historical continuity acquires special significance in the literature of socialist realism, which has absorbed all the best that humankind has created in the sphere of culture. One of the well-known genres in Uzbek poetry is Masnavi.

Masnavi (Manavi, Masnaviya), is a XIII century work written in Persian by the Sufi poet Rumi. It is one of the most famous and influential works of Sufism and Persian literature, earning its author the nickname of Mawlana, "our master". The full title of the work, Masnavi-i, can be translated as "Rhymed couplets with deep spiritual meaning".

Moreover, the word masnavi can denote a poem consisting of couplets in verses that rhyme flat, and it has come to denote a special lyrical poetic genre called masnavi(in) poetry.

Rumi's work is divided into six books and includes 424 allegorical stories illustrating the state of man in his search for God. Composed of some 25,000 couplets, the Masnavi stories draw inspiration from verses from the Qur'an, sometimes single, sometimes grouped. The work is also of historical importance, as the author regularly refers to folk beliefs and describes the different lifestyles of different occupations, different social groups, etc. For example, he describes the oldest known way to get a parrot to talk. The work also inspired by Aesop's fables, but created in order to emphasize one of the most fundamental aspects of Islam, Tawhid, i.e. monotheism.

Masnavi Genre. Even if this genre gave its name to this work, Jalal ud Din Rami is not its inventor. The poems of the Sufi Sanai - to whom we owe the Garden of Truth ("Hadîqat al-haqiqat"), one of Masnavi's masterpieces in Persian, which had a great influence on Rum by his own admission, already written in the masnavi style already in this style. This form of lyric poetry has been taken up by many authors, some of whom have long been known; we find it, for example, in the Ottoman poet Fuzuli in Layla ve Meknun (Leyla and Majnun), or in the Persian Nizami in The Five Jewels. Farid ad-Din Attar also used it in his masterpiece The Conference of Birds (Mantîq at-ayr) and in his Divine Book (Elahi-nameh).

Like Masnavi-and Ma'navi, Masnavi-style texts are long lyrical and narrative verses, sometimes instructive. The arrangement of rhymes is idiosyncratic and different from other poetic styles used in medieval Persian poetry, such as the ghazal style of love letters or the qasida style of panegyric poetry. The number of verses is infinite, and rhymes follow each other at the end of each half-line of the same couplet.

In medieval India, this style was mainly used for two types of stories: the royal panegyric and the romantic tale.

In Persia, the masnavi style was also used for novels or for telling the legend of the Parthians, as in *Vis-o Ramin* by Fakhredin Asad Gorgani.

Genre form in Arabic, Persian and Turkic literatures; a long poem written in couplets. The first monument of Turkic written literature written by masnavi is the poem "Kutadgu bilig" ("The Art of being happy") by Yusuf Balasagunsky, created in the XI century. Classical examples are Firdousi's epic "Shahnameh", poems "Five" ("Khamsa") by Nizami and others.

A poetic form in Eastern poetics, a couplet with a separate rhyme. M.'s form is characteristic of epic poetry; in lyrical poems, monorim is used, that is, one rhyme for the entire poem. Here is an excerpt from Alisher Navoi's poem "Farhad and Shirin", written in the Masnevi system:

Before on top of these mountains
My star has sent me a carpet
An angel with a wing swept that place,
Moreover, the tears of the stars sprinkled afterwards.

In addition, the heart found peace here,
Heaven bowed before me.

Looking at my sheet
Acquired here morning cleanliness.
And the evening took on its color of ink,
When the kalam blackened its tip.

Work history. The famous traveler Ibn Batta tells an anecdote about the composition of the masnavi, heard in Konya. It was said in this city that Rumi taught students in a madrasah in his youth. One day a candy sales representative came into the classroom. Rumi asked him for a cake and ate it. Then, when the merchant came out, Rumi followed him, leaving his course and his students. In addition, Ibn Battuta continues: "Because he returned very late and his disciples were waiting for him, they went to look for him, but did not find him. The Sheikh

returned a few years later. He lost his mind and could only express himself in Persian verse, the half-verses of which rhyme with each other and are incomprehensible. The students followed him, wrote down the verses he recited, and compiled a collection which they called al-Matnavi."

Many translations have been made into various languages of the Middle East, from modern Iran to India. In the work, we find a number of allusions related to carnal love to signify the love of believers for God. This was a common practice among both Christian and Muslim mystics.

However, because of these sexual allusions (although they were metaphors for the love of God), James Redhouse's first Western translation, in 1881, was poorly received by English Victorian society. However, Redhouse took pains to translate the most daring passages into Latin rather than English. However, Reynold A. Nicholson (in) who gave the first complete translation of the Masnavi into English, eight volumes published the orientalist between 1925 and 1940.

Thus, the commonality of poetic dimensions and devices in the classical literature of the East does not always make it possible to clearly and definitely identify the individual stylistic features of the work of a particular poet. Only an in-depth consideration of the ideological and artistic aspects of the work of the classics, the study of the pictorial components of innovations in the field of size and poetic techniques, the study of figurative and poetic vocabulary can reveal the originality of the work of a particular poet. Therefore, it is important and necessary for a researcher of the work of an Eastern classical poet, first of all, to treat the object of his research with deep respect, to be ready for long and hard work, to carefully study all the rich heritage that the classical literature of the East has left us.

It cannot be said that at all stages of the formation and development of Uzbek Soviet literature, the classical heritage was treated with due respect. Therefore, for a certain time, the poetic experience of the classics, the masnavi versification system, its dimensions were considered almost like museum exhibits; politically immature people attacked the rich figurative language of classical poetry, polished in the works of classical poets, capable of conveying the subtlest shades of thoughts and feelings. It was believed that the masnavi is not able to convey all the richness of modern reality.

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